

Active Learning to Enhance the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction Sector

Shannon Chance^{1,2}

¹ School of Architecture, Building & Environment Research (SABER), Technological University Dublin, Dublin, Ireland

² Centre for Engineering Education (CEE), University College London, London, United Kingdom

Email: shannon.chance@tudublin.ie; s.chance@ucl.ac.uk

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14060731>

Abstract

Active learning methods are integrated across the honors-level Bachelor of Science in Building Information Modelling (BIM/Digital Construction) at Technological University Dublin. Now in its fifth year of operation, the course provides mature students working (or aiming to work) in the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) Sector across Ireland with a wide range of well-integrated and intellectually engaging hands-on learning opportunities. The Irish government financially supports this course because the Irish AEC sector needs state-of-the-art knowledge and skills to help modernize construction methods for this small island nation. The Irish government's support underscores the significance of the course in addressing the country's well-being. Hands-on aspects of the BIM curriculum include: researching to learn about digital principles and standards; modeling using Revit, ArchiCAD, MagiCAD, and the like; combining models from various engineering and design fields and then running clash detections and developing basic cost estimates, construction plans, and animations of project phasing/sequencing using Navisworks; applying principles at work via work-based learning in each student's workplace (or in an optional, simulated work environment); designing and conducting a research thesis project that involves reviewing published literature and case studies and sometimes documenting one's own case of integrating action-research methods; building web-based portfolios to showcase one's learning; authoring multiple reflective essays to develop one's skills in reflective practice; and applying agile team management strategies to organizing a team's work and managing a team's projects. We hope the design and reporting of this course will inspire others seeking to teach BIM, support mature students and working professionals, and/or integrate active learning methods in the classes and courses they teach.

Keywords: Active Learning; Pedagogy; Building Information Modeling; Architecture; Engineering; Construction.

1 Introduction

The Bachelor of Science in Building Information Modelling (BIM/Digital Construction) at Technological University Dublin (TU Dublin) offers a comprehensive curriculum to upskill engineers and professionals who enroll from across the Republic of Ireland. Through one year of intensive study, mature students acquire the necessary expertise to earn an honors-level Bachelor of Science degree. Major components of the twelve-month curriculum are work-based learning (15 credits in the European Credit Transfer System, ECTS, as per Table 1) and developing a concise research thesis/dissertation (15 ECTS, supported by a design phase of 5 ECTS). These two components work synergistically – empowering the hands-on application of theoretical knowledge via engagement in the workplace. The research, work-based, reflective, and team-based components enable students to apply BIM principles and standards – as well as project management and research methodologies – to address real-world challenges in the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) sector.

Launched by TU Dublin in the spring of 2020, the course encompasses 60 ECTS overall. Modules meet in person one-half day per week and online two nights per week during two semesters. The cloud-based nature of BIM collaboration today provides an ideal environment for blended learning using (mostly) synchronous and (some) asynchronous approaches. Learning is mostly self-directed during the summer, where students apply new

learning in the workplace for an eight-week period with periodic advice from an academic supervisor and a workplace mentor.

Table 1. BSc (Hons) BIM module sequence

credits	module name				contact
5	Digital Construction Principles & Standards				24
10	BIM Architectural Modelling & Review	BIM Civil & Structural Modelling & Review	BIM MEP Modelling & Review	BIM Construction Model Exploitation & Review	48
10	BIM Federation & Validation				48
15	Work-Based Learning		Special Collaborative Project		16
5	Research Methods				24
15	Dissertation with Agile Project Management				30

The course's overarching goal is to equip graduates with the expertise to drive advancements in Building Information Modelling (BIM) and BIM Management (BIMM) practices throughout the Irish construction sector. Although we explicitly aim to generate new knowledge and provide an injection of new skills into the Irish AEC landscape, the methods we use hold relevance for anyone wanting to engage mature students in learning in a way that is academically rigorous and highly applied.

BIM and BIMM are essential tools in modern AEC, offering helpful solutions for digital project management. By fostering efficiency, reducing errors, and driving innovation across various project phases, BIM practices contribute to a more sustainable and productive construction industry. Consequently, the honors BSc course in BIM (Digital Construction) at TU Dublin helps inject new knowledge and skills into the Irish construction sector, enhancing the sector's overall effectiveness and competitiveness. The paper titled "Preliminary Mapping of Bachelors' Research to Enhance Digital Construction in Ireland" provides additional background on the course (Chance & McAuley, 2023a).

Consistent with the goals of Project Approaches in Engineering Education / Active Learning in Engineering (PAEE/ALE), the course design integrates many active learning (AL) methods. These are integrated into the course via group work, field- or work-based activities, project assignments, and a research thesis – all with reflective practice frameworks and project management approaches built in. The course leaders' earlier conference paper, "Infusing Research Know-How into the Construction Sector: Pedagogies to Support Digital Construction in Ireland," focused on student research (Chance & McAuley, 2023b). This paper moves the work another step forward, investigating how various AL pedagogies intersect to support student learning in BIM.

This PAEE/ALE conference paper and its presentation at PAEE/ALE 2023 are intended to help share knowledge and experience – and to support reflection and critique of the practices applied in this course. We hope that discussion during and after the presentation will help garner more diverse outsider perspectives to help us improve our course. We want it to generate new ideas for refining and extending our current approaches. The presentation will also provide audience members with new understandings of BIM, Digital Construction, and the integration of active learning across all modules of this course.

2 Literature Review

In higher education, "active learning" refers to instructional methods that actively engage students in the learning process, encouraging them to construct knowledge, solve problems, and apply concepts in meaningful ways. Active learning is recognized as an effective approach for promoting deeper understanding, critical

thinking skills, and long-term retention of information among students (Prince, 2004). It is widely used in professional education, including the fields of pharmacy (Gleason et al., 2011), medicine (Barrows & Tamblyn, 1980), teacher education (Niemi, 2002), and engineering education (Prince, 2004).

Active learning pedagogies used in higher education include group discussions, debates, problem-solving activities, case studies, role-playing sessions, and the like (Heilporn et al., 2021). Teachers interviewed by Heilporn and colleagues explained that they “enhanced student engagement” by having students discuss “a topic or study a case in teams and then share their conclusions with the whole group. While team discussions enhanced student behavioral engagement through participation, different conclusions then generated whole group debates and promoted student cognitive engagement” (p. 10). Discussion in TU Dublin’s BIM course works similarly.

Bean and Melzer (2021) discuss how writing relates to critical thinking and supports the development of such skills. They recommend providing rubrics to help direct students’ efforts, “helping students use self-assessment and peer review to promote revision and reflection” (p. 231), and using portfolios to support knowledge-generation, record-keeping, and learning assessment. TU Dublin’s BIM course uses reflective essays and e-portfolios for the purposes described by Bean and Melzer.

With a specific focus on blended learning environments and how to enhance students’ engagement in courses that blend synchronous and asynchronous learning, Heilporn et al. (2021) assessed meta-cognitive aspects of learning. They looked at “(i) the course structure and pace; (ii) the selection of teaching and learning activities; and (iii) the teacher’s role and course relationships” (p. 1). Except for the work-based learning component, our course is primarily synchronous, but it blends face-to-face and online learning.

In higher education, active learning is increasingly recognized as an essential approach for preparing students for the demands of modern professional fields, including the AEC sector. By actively engaging students in the learning process and encouraging them to construct knowledge, solve problems, and apply concepts in meaningful ways, active learning pedagogies foster more profound understanding, critical thinking skills, and long-term retention of information (Prince, 2004). This approach aligns with the dynamic and interdisciplinary nature of the AEC sector, where professionals must constantly adapt to evolving technologies, project requirements, and collaborative environments.

In the realm of engineering education, Hernández-de-Menéndez et al. (2019) described AL as “an interactive teaching method” (p. 910) and identified its primary attributes as:

- being a student-centered approach that puts the learner directly in the center of the process,
- letting students be the main protagonists of their learning process by performing meaningful activities and critically thinking about what they are doing,
- being a highly engaging method of education,
- encouraging the learner to participate actively by developing hands-on activities,
- focus students’ engagement via learning objectives,
- increasing retention and understanding of knowledge because all the learning effort is exerted by the student themselves,
- having teachers assume the role of mentors and evaluators of the progress of the students, and
- taking advantage of a vast array of aids in order to capture and maintain attention of learners. (slightly adapted from the list on p. 910)

Research by Hernández-de-Menéndez et al. (2019) found that in engineering education, “this approach supports the development of in-demand competencies such as Teamwork, Problem-solving and Analysis. In addition, students’ performance and retention rates are improved” (p. 909). The research team further noted that technology could be quite effective in helping support interactive teaching and learning in engineering.

Theoretical frameworks guiding the integration of active learning into BIM education at Technological University Dublin include Cottrell's (2023) model for facilitating critical thinking skills through analysis, reflection, and argumentation, as well as Bolton and Delderfield's (2018) guide to writing for reflective practice and professional development. Additionally, the Gibbs (1988) model provides a structured approach to guiding student reflection, which is crucial for promoting self-awareness and continuous improvement in professional practice. These frameworks serve as valuable tools for educators in designing and implementing active learning strategies that effectively prepare students for success in the modern AEC sector.

3 Active Learning Methods in BIM/Digital Construction Education

Active learning methods are integrated into every aspect of the TU Dublin BIM BSc course. Some ways we integrate AL are described in this section. We launch the course with an orientation/induction and then jump right in on the first day of the 12-month course with an 8-week-long set of two modules (depicted in Table 1). The first pair of modules covers foundational skills and knowledge.

3.1 Principles, standards, and modeling

The students all complete a 5 ECTS module on "Digital Principles and Standards" (or "DPS") together as a single cohort. For their 10 ECTS modeling modules, they break into streams (Architecture; Civil & Structural; Mechanical, Electrical, and Plumbing (MEP)) to learn to model buildings using software tools like Revit, ArchiCAD, and MagiCAD. The remaining stream, Construction Management, helps students learn to use and "exploit" models built by others, as professionals working on sites can benefit from doing. The DPS module also provides a basic introduction to academic writing and database searching; it includes research activities focusing on digital principles and standards currently underpinning BIM practice in Ireland and the UK. DPS also provides hands-on workshops in environmental sustainability and "LEAN" construction principles.

3.2 Multi-disciplinary federation and validation of models

The students bring their modeling knowledge forward in the subsequent "Federation and Validation" (F&V) module at 10 ECTS, where they work in teams of students from each stream who bring their models together, run clash detections, and resolve errors. Teachers and the students from the Construction Management stream guide each team in using Navisworks to integrate and analyze their models, and to use the software for cost estimating and construction staging/planning. The module currently uses BIM360 as a platform for collaboration.

Alongside this F&V module, students prepare for both their 8-week field-based Work-Based Learning (WBL) module (to be conducted over the summer break) and the research dissertation they will complete during the autumn semester. To prepare for the dissertation, they take a 5 ECTS module called "Research Methods" that guides them through identifying a research problem, a research question, and three research objectives aligned with methodologies for addressing the objectives and answering the research question. They need to explain the relevance of the research to their work setting and how it ties to the course.

3.3 Work-Based Learning

The "Work-Based Learning" (WBL) module allows students to apply digital methods for BIM in an approved workplace context. As the workplace context can differ significantly from student to student, the learning outcomes of the module focus on transferrable and generic skills, as well as the associated competencies identified in the frameworks of professional bodies such as Engineers Ireland, the Society of Chartered Surveyors Ireland / Royal Institution of Chartered Surveyors, and the Chartered Institute of Building (as appropriate to the individual student).

Each student also identifies a BIM-related task that requires stretching their abilities and applying new aspects of BIM, learned in the course, within their work environment. Students can: (a) undertake project that supports the completion of their Dissertation, (b) utilize Autodesk Revit, underpinned by ISO-19650 standards, to model a project previously undertaken in AutoCAD / 2D methods to demonstrate the benefits of BIM, (c) revisit a project that was undertaken without the utilization of ISO19650 or a proper BIM Execution Plan then reproduce discipline-specific project information and a range of models/model elements based on a standardized BIM Execution Plan under ISO 19650, (d) utilize Autodesk Revit to create new/bespoke families/elements modeled from existing drawings/point cloud data/existing data/supplier information OR utilize model elements/families in a new or existing project, with full ISO19650 standards implementation; (e) undertake a set of Autodesk Revit modeling tasks relevant to their role within an ISO19650 project being undertaken/planned by their organization; (f) critically document their organization's workflow and make recommendations on how a digital construction workflow can be implemented to advance data capture and communication channels; or (g) utilize Autodesk Navisworks underpinned by ISO-19650 standards, to coordinate a project that has recently used, or is currently using, 3D models to demonstrate the benefits of BIM. The project (or set of tasks) should take 15-20 days of 7.5 hours each (totalling 115-150 hours).

The remainder of the 300 WBL hours are dedicated to planning the WBL experience, including a written critique of the student's current work role versus the potential of the student's role in an organization where BIM is fully implemented on all projects. They draw from the literature and relevant professional standards (e.g., ISO16950) and frameworks (e.g., WELL, LEED, BREEAM, BSRAI, CIBSE, SCS, ASHREA, etc.) and apply these at work. They schedule, prepare a video for, attend, and report on a virtual Site Visit with their academic supervisor and work-plan mentor. They log several reflective journal entries and draft a Final Reflective Practice Report.

It is important to note that while the students are taking F&V, they also work on the work plan for their Dissertation and for WBL, both of which stress real-world applications and address current challenges faced by the students, their employers, and the larger sectors of BIM and AEC.

3.4 Research Methods and Dissertation

In the 5 ECTS "Research Methods" and 15 ECTS "Dissertation including Agile Project Management," the students learn to improve their project objectives and/or hypotheses iteratively, based on the identification of a program-related problem. They select, defend, and apply suitable academic methodologies to achieve their stated objectives. Each student conducts a critical review of current scholarly literature and relevant professional sources – reflecting upon standard theories and their inherent assumptions. The student formulates a solution for a semi-complex problem, considering ethical implications and assessing and managing risk. The students implement their proposed solution in industry-relevant settings, report and assess the outcomes of their proposed solutions (after investigating the underlying theories and examining the potential benefits of their solution to professional practice in terms of, for example, improved performance), using reliable appraisal methods. They identify deficiencies, risks, and fitness-for-purpose of their solutions; and iteratively produce a draft research paper to "starter" conference paper standard. Some of these BSc papers have gone on to presentation and publication at conferences (Martin et al., 2021; McLoughlin & McAuley, 2022; Grego et al., 2023). We are proud of the quality of the Dissertations produced and have been tracking and assessing the value of the work (see Chance & McAuley, 2023a, "Preliminary Mapping of Bachelors' Research to Enhance Digital Construction in Ireland").

The students also record the evidence for their learning journey, from problem identification to evaluation of the solution, in an appropriate structure using a personal e-portfolio and reflect upon their learning, particularly about integrating the knowledge gained in previous modules, using both continuous and summative entries

to a personal, online e-portfolio (using Adobe Portfolio with One Drive file storage). Building the web-based portfolios is intended to showcase students' learning and help students direct some of their efforts to recognize what and how they learn and consider how to improve over time. In this, they author reflective essays to develop reflective practice skills.

During the Dissertation module, the students are guided to apply agile project management strategies, including SCRUMs (a form of management used for software development), that help teams respond quickly and effectively to quickly changing content and the incremental development, testing, and release of new software products.

Throughout the course, the students can access an extensive array of BIM, collaboration, project management, and presentation software platforms and tools. They get exposure to LinkedIn Learning (LIL) for self-directed exploration, and many of them upload certificates of completion for related LIL courses (e.g., Dynamo, project management, facilities management) even after graduation.

3.5 Learning Outcomes of the Course

Learners must demonstrate the required learning outcomes at this BSc course's end. They each create a discipline-specific BIM model utilizing industry-leading software and relevant standards. They utilize appropriate BIM standards and guidance materials within appropriate workflows. They effectively coordinate BIM models among disciplines and determine the effectiveness of processes and standards associated with BIM coordination. In this, they exploit BIM models for a range of tasks related to coordination, cost, energy, and design, and they validate the outcomes. They also define the requirements for low-energy building construction and interpret the outcomes of decisions around building materials and methods. They use and evaluate various digital and cloud-based technologies and tools to support multidisciplinary coordination and workflows.

Because we have four different streams, some learning outcomes vary. However, by the end of the course, most learners will also be able to create BIM objects and families, utilize BIM modeling software to achieve energy targets, and incorporate various information sources into BIM models (e.g., point clouds, existing building surveys, and facilities management information).

The curriculum is designed to align with TU Dublin's Graduate Attributes, which aim to foster enterprising skills such as innovation, leadership, collaboration, and entrepreneurship. Through workshops, engagement opportunities, and collaboration with TU Dublin's support services, professional bodies, organizations, and employers, the program aims to enhance students' job readiness. Professional development is integrated from the program's outset to support a variety of learners (specifically, those already in employment, those seeking role changes, and those currently unemployed or returning to work after a career break) with tailored re-entry workshops facilitated by industry experts.

Students are encouraged to develop target attributes, including becoming innovative leaders and effective collaborators in BIM. Teachers emphasize the importance of global responsibility, ethical conduct, motivation, and effective communication – within teams and across engineering fields. Inquiry-based approaches cultivate learners' critical thinking, problem-solving, knowledge creation, and decision-making skills. The program emphasizes disciplinary knowledge, reflective practice, work-based learning, and digital literacy, promoting continuous improvement and preparation for careers where ongoing learning is essential. Effective teamwork, emotional intelligence, strategic thinking, and resilience are also emphasized to prepare students for success in the collaborative environment of BIM coordination.

4 Assessment and Quality Assurance Procedures

Although a detailed description of quality assurance is beyond the scope of this report, it is worth noting that the course is rigorously assessed via formal procedures. These include continual data collection, course-refinement activities, and twice-annual assessments by external examiners who provide feedback and have helped hone the course over the years.

Assessment and quality assurance (QA) at TU Dublin is coordinated by the Program Chair, Head of Discipline, and the college's Head of Learning Development. The course was validated by Ireland's Higher Education Authority (HEA) in 2018 and is continuously reviewed today. We use structured rubrics to assess student performance; they help us provide formative and summative feedback in most modules and support reliable and replicable reviews by multiple staff members. Most grades are determined by two teachers, and we assess the evaluations for consistency – in any instance where the scores of two raters vary by 15% or more, we enlist a third reviewer.

All grades are uploaded by the respective module teachers and reviewed by a Module Board. This Board includes two external examiners – one from industry and one from another academic institution offering similar subjects – to help ensure validity, coverage, rigor, and fairness.

A Program Review committee (comprised of a student representative from each stream and all staff teaching the course) meets each semester to consider student feedback, address emerging concerns, and identify action items to enhance the course design and delivery.

We also conduct surveys and combine the results with the evaluations gathered from the Program Committee into formal reports. All agendas, minutes, and reports are provided to students and staff for review and to ensure open communication.

Statements from the most recent external examiners' report (2023) tie directly to topics highlighted in the literature review above, on active learning:

"The **Project-based approach**, both at individual and group level, is very practical and reflects industry situations." Moreover, "**Practical project-based approach** to teaching BIM/Digital Construction using multi-discipline **teams** reflects Industry situation."

"Programme content is extensive and all modules are relevant to Industry needs [both present and future]. While the volume of content and assignments seems intensive, it allows students to sample potential areas of BIM/Digital Construction through further studies or within Industry."

"Most students benefitted from the **Reflective Learning process**."

"Marking schemes for modules correctly reflect the practical focus of Module learning outcomes" and "Marking of assignments was very fair and consistent across all students and modules. Students were given every opportunity and support to achieve their best result through constant feedback and marking rubrics in particular." Additionally, "The level of **engagement, support and feedback from staff**, in particular the **marking rubrics** and the sense of an open-door approach, provides students the greatest opportunities to develop their skills and reach their potential."

The 2022 report from a different examiner stated, "The program was consistently and fairly marked. The **marking rubric** layout clearly where marks were gained and lost and provide good feedback to students."

The 2022 report from a third examiner explain that the "Comprehensive **grading rubrics** [provide] clarity for students and supports consistency where multiple examiners are involved." The evaluator noted improvement in the course design over time: "The one aspect for improvement that I raised following my first visit was to

reconsider evidence provided to demonstrate that students had achieved the learning outcomes in relation to the 'WKPL 1004 – **Work Based Learning**' module. As a 15 ECTS module [...] its significance in contributing to overall programme outcomes should not be underestimated. To the credit of the programme team, they have responded and the module is developing positively and builds on the success of the first year. Again, the inclusion of this module is to be commended as the inclusion of significant work placement elements is beginning to realise increased prevalence in third level education and the development of such modules can prove challenging."

5 Reflection and Critique of Current Practices

A snapshot of our ongoing and structured approach to evaluating the effectiveness of our active learning pedagogies for helping achieve course objectives is provided above. The strengths of the current course structure are reflected in the quality of the models and collaborations as well as the WBL and research outputs generated to date. Weaknesses in the current course structure are the very high level of engagement students must sustain for 12 continuous months; that said, the degree they earn (an honors-level bachelor's degree founded on Recognition of Prior Learning) is prestigious and very well recognized across the Irish AEC sector.

Through Ireland's well-established QA process, the staff, led by the Program Chair (Shannon Chance) and the Head of Discipline (Barry McAuley), have continually identified and addressed areas for improvement – many of these related to streamlining the submission requirements to avoid unnecessary duplication of work and harmonizing the schedule. We periodically run pilot tests of scheduling refinements to achieve just-in-time delivery of content that the students can immediately apply.

As one cohort of students seemed unaware of the time-consuming nature of the course, in December 2022, we started conducting a pre-orientation to help students visualize what lay ahead so they could plan accordingly. The student has indicated that this helped them prepare and acclimate. The 2023 external examiner's report explained, "Students were thankful for the Pre-induction process as it highlighted the level of commitment required for the course and motivated them to set-up support systems to help e.g., with family or work."

Despite the (pre-induction and induction) emphasis on allocating enough time, some students still drop the course in the first month. We find this unfortunate, but also acknowledge that our drop-out rate is in line with these types of training courses for job-seekers. The required commitment is high as this is the equivalent of a full year of full-time study (60 ECTS). Most of our students complete it on top of full-time employment and the family responsibilities that mature students often balance.

Just a week before the writing of this paper, we found ways to streamline our WBL experience a bit more, for example. We removed the reflective journal entry used to report the outcomes of the site visit and tucked this expectation into the Final Reflective Practice Report (where students are provided an outline of points to address). We removed the requirement to make a formal WBL presentation at the end of the summer, as this requirement seemed to present a mental block for students to embrace the work fully necessary for their Dissertations until after the presentation date. The short video that we now request they produce for the virtual Site Visit is used in lieu, but the Final Reflective Practice Report still requires them to make the critical appraisals that were previously presented to 4-5 other peers.

6 Future Directions and Implications

In the coming years, we will need to assess how the changes to the WBL module play out – to ensure that we are still meeting the full range of Learning Objectives specified in our Module Descriptor.

We recently applied for a few modifications to the set of Module Descriptors validated initially in 2018. We more explicitly called out the integration of sustainability, ethics, and diversity issues into various modules.

Our biggest challenge has been introducing mature students to academic writing, as this is not part of their day-to-day job, and most have not done this at the university level before. We have found that they are well up to the challenge, given a structured approach with limited options (there is no time in this condensed format for them to collect survey or interview data, so their research relies on literature review, case study, and/or action research methods). We have had good results by encouraging students to integrate their WBL and Dissertation work as much as possible, so that they conduct a lot of their research design and literature review prior to commencing WBL, so that they can apply techniques and collect data in situ – that they can subsequently write up for the Dissertation module.

We have tested various timings for the delivery of the Research Methods module, and currently provide most of that structure learning during the spring semester, with the final research Proposal Form (research work plan) presented and written up for submission at the end of the summer.

One challenge has been to hit the optimal level of work for the Dissertation. Based on our prior research (Chance & McAuley, 2023a, 2023b), we recognized that there might not be enough distinction in quality between our MSc and BSc dissertation outputs. We made more explicit the option for students to use literature reviews and published case studies (i.e., secondary research) to answer all objectives. We also pilot-tested a drop from 6000 words ($\pm 10\%$) to 5000 words. In the coming iteration, we will allow anything in the range of 5000-6000 \pm .

As active learning pedagogies are embedded in every aspect of these modules, we do not see the need to add new AL components. We will, however, look for additional ways to streamline so that we get the most authentic learning – and the greatest positive effect from the students' engagement.

Yet, we note the great potential for broader application of active learning methods in similar educational programs in Ireland and beyond. Moreover, considering the implications of this present study for BIM education and the AEC sector in Ireland, and in light of findings from Chance and McAuley (2023a, 2023b), we now propose to conduct a new study to evaluate the effectiveness of the BIM/Digital Construction courses at TU Dublin in nurturing leaders who have made significant contributions to the Irish AEC sector. By engaging graduates from our various BIM courses, we intend to assess the career trajectories and leadership roles these individuals have assumed following their BIM education. For this, we propose to adopt a leadership model, e.g., Fullan (2007) or Black and Gregerson (2013) – and then develop a survey instrument around the model and conduct it with all graduates of our BSc and MSc BIM courses.

7 Conclusion

A prior review of bachelor's research topics by Chance and McAuley (2023a) provided insights into the focus areas for BIM students. A common thread across the BSc dissertations was an emphasis on national-level issues, with many students exploring the possibilities of new processes or tools, especially in architecture and construction. Topics including LEAN practices, heritage conservation, and modular prefabrication were common. Of the 59 BSc dissertation studies completed by that date, three had achieved significant recognition, contributing to areas like energy-efficient design (Grego, et al., 2023), structural design optimization (McLoughlin & McAuley, 2022), and enhancement of estate management within the healthcare sector (Martin et al., 2021).

The Chance and McAuley (2023a) paper stressed the importance of research skills in shaping students into effective practitioners. With students now assuming leadership roles and driving changes within the Irish construction sector, the next step is to understand the real impact of TU Dublin's BIM courses. The research team will soon shift focus toward surveying past students – in order to assess how well the BIM courses have equipped individuals to contribute as leaders in the Irish AEC sector.

In conclusion, this paper has provided a chance to reflect upon the importance of active learning in BIM education and its impact on student learning and professional development. Ongoing reflection is necessary – not just as a skill for our students to learn – but as a crucial activity for helping us improve the design and delivery of this course, which holds great relevance and promises to enhance AEC practices across Ireland.

Acknowledgments

This report draws from curriculum documents by Avril Behan and Deborah Brennan on behalf of TU Dublin (formerly the Dublin Institute of Technology). Their unique contributions laid the foundation for the very successful course we provide today.

8 References

- Bolton, G., & Delderfield, R. (2018). *Reflective practice: Writing and professional development*. London, UK: SAGE Publications Ltd.
- Barrows, H. S., & Tamblyn, R. M. (1980). *Problem-based learning: An approach to medical education* (Vol. 1). Springer Publishing Company.
- Bean, J. C., & Melzer, D. (2021). *Engaging ideas: The professor's guide to integrating writing, critical thinking, and active learning in the classroom*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Black, J. S., & Gregersen, H. (2013). *It starts with one: Changing individuals changes organizations*. Pearson Education.
- Chance, S. & McAuley, B. (2023a). Preliminary Mapping of Bachelors' Research to Enhance Digital Construction in Ireland. Paper presented at the European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI). DOI: 10.21427/8FK0-6R60
- Chance, S. & McAuley, B. (2023b). Infusing Research Know-How into the Construction Sector: Pedagogies to Support Digital Construction in Ireland. Paper presented at 2023 ASEE Annual Conference & Exposition, Baltimore, MD. DOI: 10.21427/B7WA-5W45
- Cottrell, S. (2023). *Critical Thinking Skills: Effective Analysis, Argument and Reflection*. London, UK: Palgrave.
- Fullan, M. (2007). *Leading in a culture of change*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Gibbs, G. (1988). *Learning by doing: A guide to teaching and learning methods*. Oxford Polytechnic: Oxford.
- Gleason, B. L., Peeters, M. J., Resman-Targoff, B. H., Karr, S., McBane, S., Kelley, K., ... & Denetclaw, T. H. (2011). An active-learning strategies primer for achieving ability-based educational outcomes. *American journal of pharmaceutical education*, 75(9), 186.
- Grego, A., Chance, S. and McAuley, B. (2023). *Using BIM to increase the efficiency of energy - driven retrofitting projects*. Proceedings of the EUBIM 2023 - BIM International Conference, Valencia, 17th - 20th May, Pp 142-151, DOI: 10.21427/YPBK-9M63
- Heilporn, G., Lakhali, S., & Béglise, M. (2021). An examination of teachers' strategies to foster student engagement in blended learning in higher education. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 18(1), 25.
- Hernández-de-Menéndez, M., Vallejo Guevara, A., Tudón Martínez, J. C., Hernández Alcántara, D., & Morales-Menendez, R. (2019). Active learning in engineering education. A review of fundamentals, best practices and experiences. *International Journal on Interactive Design and Manufacturing (IJDeM)*, 13, 909-922 .
- Martin, M., Boch, A., & Furlong, K. (2021). Can the implementation of Building Information Modelling (Digital Construction) improve delivery of Capital Projects (Design and Construction) for the Health Service in association with the development of a new National Estates Information System? Proceedings of the CitA BIM Gathering 2021, September 21-23 in Dublin, Ireland.
- McLoughlin, J. & McAuley, B. (2022). Optimising existing digital workflow for structural engineering organisations through the partnering of BIM and Lean processes, Proceedings of the Civil Engineering Research in Ireland 2022 conference, 25-26th of August, Dublin, pp 159 – 170.
- Niemi, H. (2002). Active learning—a cultural change needed in teacher education and schools. *Teaching and teacher education*, 18(7), 763-780.
- Prince, M. (2004). Does active learning work? A review of the research. *Journal of engineering education*, 93(3), 223-231.